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Abbreviations in Homonymy

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Abstract

This article discusses the phenomenon of homonymy in the field of abbreviation. Until now, homonymy has rarely been considered along with the topic of abbreviations, and yet it is all closely interconnected, since the frequency of using homonymous abbreviations in English literature is quite high. Despite the fact that there are quite numerous, albeit fragmentary, studies on the problems of abbreviation in modern languages, there is a small amount of research in the field of abbreviation-homonymous relations, abbreviated lexical units remain in many respects a mystery in linguistic terms, since in relation to them one has to consider from a specific point of view such fundamental problems as the problem of the structure of a word and its meaning, the problem of a morpheme, etc. This complexity explains the heterogeneity of opinions, and sometimes a contradictory approach to homonymous abbreviated lexical units.

Keywords: Homonymy, Abbreviation, Acronyms, Homoacronyms, Phenomenon

1. Introduction

One of the phenomena inherent in all languages and characterizing the lexical-semantic system of each language is homonymy. Due to the fact that this phenomenon is widespread in many languages and is of great importance for characterizing the lexical-semantic system of a language, the problem of homonymy attracts the attention of both domestic and foreign linguists.

Homonymy is a phenomenon that directly follows from the fact of the ambiguity of the plan of expression and the plan of the content of the language. Thus, the problem of homonymy turns out to be part of a more general problem of the relationship between form and content in a language, which makes it necessary to study it in depth. Homonymy is a manifestation of that special property of a linguistic sign, due to which identical signifiers can correspond to different signifieds. Thus, the study of the phenomenon of homonymy also meets the needs of applied linguistics. Homonymy is a certain obstacle in the process of communication. Often the listener finds himself at a loss as to which of the several different meanings expressed by a given language form should be chosen in order to correctly understand the message. Difficulties can arise not only for the listener, but also for the speaker, who, in order to optimize the communication process, tries to build the statement so that it can be understood unambiguously. Homonymy introduces difficulties in the process of mastering a foreign language by pupils and students, because the analysis of such forms significantly complicates the perception of a foreign text or message. Homonymy causes no less difficulties when building systems for automatic text processing, as well

as in lexicographic work – when determining the boundaries between individual words, when developing ways to represent homonyms in a dictionary, when choosing frequency counting units dictionary, etc. In turn, this leads to difficulties and problems in translation.

Homonymy is the hindrance in communication. Participants, which are the necessary prerequisites of any communicative act, include a sender of the message, its recipient and hindrances that homonymy brings in. Due to hindrances the message is perceived by the recipient with such a meaning, which was not foreseen by a sender (Pukaliak, 2018). The beginning of the process of shortening words dates back to ancient times. The abbreviation in various types of written speech is as old as the written language itself. The abbreviation (from Latin *abbrevio* – I shorten) traces its history back to the Sumerians, whose writing is considered the first recorded on Earth (4th century BC). Ancient scientists and rhetoricians believed that the newly formed abbreviated units had a different emotional coloring compared to those full variants of these units that traditionally expressed this meaning. Words can be used as a linguistic means of influencing and influencing the addressee of speech. Modern English has developed the abbreviation Xmas < Christmas, which goes back to the Greek words Christ < Khri'stos, X < chi, p.Chr.n. < post Christum natum (from the birth of Christ).

Based on the fact that abbreviation processes reflect the logic characteristic of the development of any national language, striving for the simplicity of linguistic expression and the preservation of its informational significance for communication purposes, it is believed that abbreviation originally arose only as a means of economy in writing, only much later (in English language – in the 16th century, in Russian – at the end of the 19th century), abbreviated units began to first appear in colloquial speech and only then move into the styles of written speech, the exceptions, of course, are terminology and author's neology. Reading graphic abbreviations by name by letter names, gradually forming these readings into a stable word – this is one of the ways to the first lexical abbreviations in many languages. Gradually, the number of abbreviations increased markedly.

Another circumstance that arises as a result of the prevalence of abbreviations, namely, the formation of homonyms. We note in passing that it is the large number of short monosyllabic words in English that largely explains the prevalence of homonymy in this language. Indeed, longer words can match in one part and differ in another part, while shorter ones are more likely to match completely, hence the numerous homonyms, such as can – I can and can – preserve.

Homonyms that arise on the basis of abbreviations can be represented in the form of two fundamentally different groups – one group consists of abbreviations that coincide with existing full words, for example, CAR – Canadian Association of Radiologists, CAT – Civil Air Transport. Especially many of these homonyms arise due to truncations like campaign – camp, artillery – art, as a result of which camp – an abbreviation for campaign and the full word camp – camp coincide.

Another group of homonyms are polysemantic abbreviations. When reducing various polysyllabic words, their first parts may coincide, forming homonyms – abbreviations, for example: sub – subaltern, sub – subeditor, sub – subject, sub – subjunctive, sub – sublimation, sub – submarine, sub – subscription. Homonymous abbreviations are even more numerous, arising from the fact that various names consisting of several words with the same letters form homonyms, for example: RTC – Railway Transport Corps, RTC – Recruit Training Centre, RTC – Reserve Training Corps, RTC – Royal Tanks Corps. If the homonyms of the first group (such as art – artillery and art – art) practically cannot disrupt communications, since they are usually used in various contexts, situations, etc., then the homonyms of the second group can introduce some confusion into the acts of communication.

2. Objective of the study

The purpose of the work is to give a general description of abbreviated lexical units and the linguistic phenomenon of homonymy, defining the relationship between them, identifying the difficulties of translating homonymous abbreviations and suggesting ways to solve them.

3. Methodology

Research methods include direct contextual analysis, cognitive-linguistic, or linguistic description. With the help of this method the main features of abbreviations in homonymy is clarified. The investigation of the problem may be considered completely for it is not possible to cover all the study by using one method. That is why the study of these concepts is needed to investigate deeply.

4. Presentation and discussion

Abbreviations of words are widespread in both oral and written speech. Of course, most abbreviations first appeared in oral speech, and then gradually entered written speech. They are found in many words of Latin-French origin. In modern English, abbreviations are mostly used in military documents (especially in the United States). About half of the words used in such documents consist of abbreviations (Borisov, 1972). Abbreviations are also widely used in technical and specialized literature. In fiction, they are used relatively little, except for the abbreviated forms of auxiliary verbs: `ll (shall, will) and `d (had, would, should) and so on. These abbreviated forms of auxiliary verbs are mainly used with personal pronouns and are often found in the direct speech of the heroes of the work, even in the speech of the author. In general, various types of abbreviations are more widely developed in modern English than in Azerbaijani (Arakin, 1958).

Due to the variety in their structure, cuts are very different. In the formation of homonyms, they can be grouped as follows:

- 1) An abbreviated word is homonymous with another unabbreviated word. For example: flu(e) – clever (abbreviated from the word influenza) – flue (chimney), flue (fur), flue (fishing net);
hip – dejection (derived from the word hypochondria) means "spirit" and "disheartened" and is homonymous with the word "hip", hip (deaf) -hip- (the part where the human body and leg join) etc.
tick – giving or receiving loans and loans – tic (irritability) (derived from the word ticket)
tick (the face of the bed), tick (tick, tick);
tract – tract (derived from the word tractate) – tract (land, forest), water area, uninterrupted strip;
- 2) Abbreviation of auxiliary verbs with personal pronouns and homonymization with unabbreviated words.

For example,

- I'll (I + shall or will) – isle (island) and aisle (passage between rows);
- I'd (I + had or would or should) – eyed (eye – the past tense and past participle of the verb to observe);
- he'd (he + had or would or should) – heed (carefully and carefully watch); we'd (we + had or would or should) – weed.

It is distinguished by the grammatical homonymy of the morpheme `d, which was formed as a result of shortening the auxiliary verbs had, would, should (Tishler, 1988).

- 3) An abbreviated word is homonymous with another abbreviated word. For example:
gin – a trap, to ensnare (derived from the word gin) – gin – gooseberry ore (derived from the word Geneva);
spec – trade (derived from the word speculation) – speck – spot, stain (derived from the word speckles);
van – vanguard (derived from the word vanguard) – van – van, cart (derived from the word caravan).

In English homonymy, there are cases of homonymization of abbreviations called acronyms with different words. Acronyms are capitalized abbreviations that are read not as letters but as words according to the phonetic norms of the English language. When creating acronyms, they try to make them easier to remember and pronounce, so that such abbreviations form homonyms with any common word. For example, man (Military Aviation Notice) is an order to ensure the flight safety of military aircraft (abbreviated from the word ink) – man – man; mass (Modern Army Supply System) the new supply system of the US ground forces (abbreviated form of the word ink) – mass – mass, bulk, collect, collect.

Such homonymization is very convenient during communication, as it helps to remember military terms, and also saves time and paper. But such homonyms are not of great linguistic interest.

Thus, the role of homonyms is great, both in enriching the vocabulary of the language and in order to express subtle meanings in the language.

In the 21st century, brevity has become the closest sister of not only talent, but also a close friend of most Internet users. Brevity is sometimes a close relative of saving time and money. If Pushkin were alive, he would have gone bankrupt by sending sms, write every time "I remember a wonderful moment, you appeared in front of me ..." instead of the modern "ILY" (I Love You). Be sure, sending another "SY" (see you), that the interlocutor will understand you correctly. We also advise you not to write such messages to older people and do not forget that in oral speech such words sound at least strange, but for your grandmother it is also intimidating. How not to get lost in the world of abbreviations read below and right now! The most common and short ones do not need a lengthy introduction. For those whose eye hurts "a lot of letters", Anglophiles have adapted the following spellings of common words:

b – be, **asap** – as soon as possible, **b4** – before, **bout** – about, **C** – see, **dey** – they **idk** – I don't know, **l8er** – later, **gr8** – great, **str8** – straight, **tyl** – talk to you later **wht** – what, **w8** – wait, **U, Y** – you, **u2** – you too, **cnt** – can't, **gd** – good, **luv** – love **n** – and, **r** – are, **1t** – want, **2** – too, to, **2day** – today, **4** – for

In recent years, there has been a crisis of oversaturation of the language with initial abbreviations that are inconvenient for pronunciation and difficult to remember. But the language coped with this crisis by internal means: the tendency to lexicalize abbreviations intensified, as a result of which a qualitatively new way of abbreviation appeared – homoacronymy, which refers to the creation of abbreviated units that coincide in their phonetic structure with commonly used words (Voloshin, 1966). Homoacronyms are very special, unique lexical units; these are acronyms homonymous with ordinary words: *CAT* "college of advanced technology" – higher technical college and a cat "cat"; *DEM* "design for economic manufacture", *dem* "demodulator" 'demodulator', *TOP* "tobacco prevention" 'smoking warning', a top 'the highest point of something', developed and important degree of abbreviation. They are especially willing to resort to homoacronymy when creating special terms, which is quite understandable: the abundance of terms makes it difficult to remember them, but "fitted" to any well-known and commonly used word, they quickly enter into speech use, and then become fixed in the language, since the stereotype of abbreviation forms makes it possible to easily store them in memory (DVD "Digital Video Disk", hydroelectric power station). As a model, not only the most familiar word is chosen, but also such that its meaning is associated with the internal form, the meaning of this term. At the same time, morphological and lexical aspects closely interact in the formation of homoacronyms: the first determines the structure of the homoacronym, the second determines its semantics (Borisov, 1972). This phenomenon is called correlative abbreviation, under which V.V. Borisov, who has comprehensively studied the features of abbreviated units and, especially, acronyms, understands the process of parallel, simultaneous creation of abbreviation and correlate, as well as cases of selecting new correlates to existing values (Borisov, 1972). Homoacronyms are often used to obtain an advertising effect, a psychological impact on the recipient. Thus, they facilitate the work of the translator, suggesting to him the purpose of this object, indicating its properties: BEST "blitz electro shock therapy" and the best "best". Returning from homoacronyms to abbreviations in general, it should be noted that an abbreviation is usually unambiguous if you focus on its referent. Here, however, we have to add that, at the same time, many of the abbreviations with different referents have the same or approximately the same alphabetic (syllabic) composition (Varina, 2004), the same graphic form: with almost complete lack of motivation for these units (for example, initial abbreviations) even in a broad context, such homonymy creates tangible difficulties.

English and American abbreviations, made up of the initials M and R in different combinations (MP, M / P, M. P., mp, m. p., mP), denote 28 different concepts, including as many as five types of police: Marine Police, Metropolitan Police (London), Military Police, Mounted Police, Municipal Police.

A deliberately created pair is curious: CAT (homonym English, "cat") and MOUSE (homonym English, "mouse"), and the purpose of the cat – CAT (Celestial Atomic Trajectory = space rocket with a nuclear charge) – to destroy the mouse – MOUSE (Minimum Orbital Unmanned Satellite Earth = artificial Earth satellite without a crew with a minimum orbit).

Such cases are a tangled tangle of meanings and allusions, which is a play on words. In order to more clearly show examples of homonymous abbreviations, let's turn to the context and take the abbreviation AC as an example:

1) – aircraft carrier

When the U.S. Navy really needs to impress people, it flies them out to one of its super AC. Standing 20 stories above the water and stretching 1,092 feet (333 meters) from bow to stern (about as long as the 77-story Chrysler Building is tall), the sheer bulk of these ships is awe-inspiring. But the really amazing thing about a supercarrier isn't its size; it's the intense scene on its flight deck." [www.howstuffworks.com/aircraft-carrier.htm]

2) alternating current – alternating current

"The number of cycles per second is the frequency of the alternating current, the most common AC frequency being 50 c.p.s."

"We know the AC to be continually changing its direction."

3) air-conditioning – air conditioning

"How to survive without AC? You will need: a fan, ice, linen sheets, spicy food, wristbands, a bandanna, and a window fan exhaust."

4) analog computer – AVM

"These are different from a digital computer because an AC can perform several mathematical operations simultaneously. It uses continuous variables for mathematical operations and utilizes mechanical or electrical energy." [www.buzzle.com/articles/different-types-of-computers.html]

5) access control

"Electronic AC uses computers to solve the limitations of mechanical locks and keys. A wide range of credentials can be used to replace mechanical keys. The electronic AC system grants access based on the credential presented. When access is granted, the door is unlocked for a predetermined time and the transaction is recorded. When access is refused, the door remains locked and the attempted access is recorded."

6) adaptive control

"This work is devoted to exploration of approaches of multilevel control organization in autonomous AC systems. Examined approach is based on the concept of decomposition of subsystems of autonomous AC system into layers, each of them is corresponding to appropriate control level. Implementation of this approach in applied control system of the given controlled object – mobile robot, has been demonstrated. Results of experimental researches of developed control system properties have been presented.."

7) automatic computer

"FLAC, the Florida Automatic Computer, was an early digital electronic computer built for the United States Air Force at Patrick Air Force Base (PAFB), Florida to perform missile data reduction. The computer began service in 1953." [dbpedia.org/page/Florida_Automatic_Computer]

8) axiom of choice There are a number of weaker axioms which are implied by the full axiom of choice. Some of these are valid or accepted more generally than the full AC, and/or suffice for some of the usual applications of choice."

9) account current – current account

"Bank free of maintenance and transaction fees with an AIB Personal SA(AC)."

10) administrative county – administrative county

"An AC was an administrative division in England and Wales and Ireland used for the purposes of local government. They are now abolished, although in Northern Ireland their former areas are used as the basis for lieutenancy." [Amazon.com: Familypedia]

11) Appellate Court -

Many U.S. lawyers title their AC a court of appeal or court of appeals. Historically, others have titled their AC a court of errors (or court of errors and appeals), on the premise that it was intended to correct errors made by lower courts."

12) abdominal cavity

After the peritoneum is opened, identify the major organs as they lie within the AC.

In this dissection, the lower part of the peritoneum has been reflected downward in order to display the peritoneal folds in this region:

lateral peritoneal fold lpf produced by the inferior epigastric artery.

medial peritoneal fold mpf produced by the embryonic umbilical arteries."

We noted a qualitatively new way of abbreviation – homoacronymy. Homoacronyms are very special, unique lexical units; These are acronyms that are homonymous with common words. They are especially willing to resort to homoacronymy when creating special terms, to obtain an advertising effect, etc. In the formation of homoacronyms, morphological and lexical aspects closely interact: the first determines the structure of the homoacronym, the second determines its semantics. This phenomenon is called correlative abbreviation. Returning from homoacronyms to abbreviations in general, we noted that the abbreviation, as a rule, is unambiguous, if you focus on its referent, but at the same time, many of the abbreviations with different referents have the same or approximately the same letter (syllabic) composition, the same graphic form: with the almost complete lack of motivation of these units, even in a broad context, such homonymy creates tangible difficulties, which can be seen from the many illustrative examples with the use of homonymous abbreviations.

From a translation point of view, such abbreviations can be seen as a potential source of error and as a difficult translation task. In case of accidental, unintentional coincidence of the abbreviation form with any other word, the translation of the abbreviation is carried out on a general basis, as if there were no such homonymy.

But “intentionality” is considered completely differently if the homonymy is used by the author for a certain stylistic purpose, or if the decoding is “tailored” to a common language word, that is, it is deciphered as if it were not an abbreviation, or with the so-called “joking transcripts, etc. All these are puns, the successful transfer of which to the TL is a difficult, and sometimes impossible task.

Consider the following example. How to translate a playful transcript of Amer. NASA – Never a straight answer – “never (giving) a direct answer”. In its actual meaning, National Aeronautics and Space Administration, the abbreviation is transferred unchanged into French and German and transcribed into Russian and Bulgarian; therefore, it is possible to translate a pun by issuing a playful phrase of four meaningful words beginning with the letters H, A, C and A. Depending on the specific case and the stylistic task set, other solutions are possible: one of them is simply to give the decoding a comic meaning, not corresponding to the real one, for example, “National absolutely ridiculous administration” (Barkhudarov, 2003).

Of course, homonymous abbreviations present a particular difficulty for translation. The issue of the recipient's perception of English abbreviations is becoming more and more relevant. Due to the special tendency of the English language to compression, economy of language means, simplification of grammatical structures, we have a well-developed system of abbreviations and broad prospects for its further development. On the one hand, these are endless opportunities for creating ever new abbreviations, their speedy adaptation in the English language system, on the other hand, these are certain difficulties associated with contradictions in this system, with its imperfection. First of all, these are the problems of translating abbreviations. The accuracy and unambiguity of the abbreviation is important in any field of science, therefore, a special approach is needed to translate this kind of language units. In English, there is a tendency to shorten any term. The Russian language lags far behind in the quantitative sense of abbreviations: what is called a term in Russian, in English turns into an abbreviation: LN “liquid nitrogen” “liquid nitrogen”.

The abbreviation, as a rule, is unambiguous, and this, as we have already said, makes translation easier. Here, however, it is necessary to recall that, at the same time, many of the abbreviations with different referents have the same or approximately the same literal (syllabic) composition, the same graphic form: despite the almost complete lack of motivation of these units (for example, initial abbreviations), even in a wide context, such homonymy creates tangible difficulties and causes translation errors. Even in a special text, it is not always possible to be sure of the correct choice of abbreviations – for example, the English abbreviation SRF stands for Supplemental Reserve Facility (a mechanism for financing additional reserves) and special reserve fund (special reserve fund), and RI can also be deciphered as a proper name Rhode Island (Rhode Island), and as a routing indicator (the address part of the message header). In this case, we can talk either about homonymy – the coincidence of the form of one abbreviation with the form of another, or about the coincidence with the full form of a completely different word.

From a translation point of view, such abbreviations can be seen as a potential source of errors. In case of accidental, unintentional coincidence of the abbreviation form with any other word, the translation of the abbreviation is carried out on a general basis, as if there were no such homonymy (WHO – World Health Organization is translated into Russian as WHO, and not as WHO- кро).

When translating abbreviations, decoding is used; deciphering is the establishment of a correlate and determination of the meaning of a given abbreviation in a particular context.

The problem of abbreviation attracts more and more attention of linguists. The widespread use of a wide variety of abbreviations is a kind of language response to the scientific and technological revolution taking place in the world. And it is not surprising that the abbreviation is used most intensively to replenish the vocabulary of new, rapidly developing branches of science and technology: astronautics, nuclear energy, programming, etc. Abbreviation has recently become one of the most productive ways to replenish the vocabulary of many languages. The number of abbreviated lexical units in developed languages is tens of thousands.

Informative capacity, ease of pronunciation, easy memorability of abbreviations contribute to the growth of their number and use in various areas of communication, and hence the need for their study increases. The studies devoted to the problems of abbreviation contain many controversial and contradictory statements. There is still a lot of uncertainty about the nature of abbreviations, about their relationship with the language system, there is no strict, clear classification of the structural types of abbreviated lexical units. This work is an attempt to fill one of these gaps by considering the issue of homonymy in the field of abbreviation.

5. Conclusion

Abbreviation is one of the most popular and productive ways of word formation today, which is used not only in Russian or English, but also in all European languages. The history of abbreviation from the moment of its inception to the present day has more than a dozen years, however, students of a foreign language often do not pay due attention to this method of word formation. Meanwhile, the study of abbreviation is becoming an obvious necessity today, without which it is impossible to imagine the general picture of word formation, since the abbreviation serves almost all spheres of human activity. Abbreviations help to minimize speech effort, language tools and time, while remaining clear and easy to understand. Abbreviations are also necessary in order to simplify long names in formal business speech. At the same time, words with a complex internal structure have a compressed external form, which allows them to be used both in colloquial speech and in scientific works. Abbreviations-tours, gaining mass distribution in special spheres, are included as equal words in the speech of the whole people. The modern state of languages is characterized by the processes of globalization, which have led to the emergence of a special kind of names for objects, concepts and concepts, together with increased requirements for speech economy, as a result of which a huge layer of abbreviated vocabulary has arisen. Interest in the specifics of creating abbreviated nominations in different languages and in the peculiarities of their use in various types and genres of speech is due to the fact that abbreviation turns out to be one of the word-formation methods that meet the pragmatic attitudes of our time. The term "abbreviation" in modern domestic linguistics means the process, "a way of creating nominations for those concepts and realities that were originally designated descriptively, using attributive phrases", and "abbreviation-round" is the result of this process. The abbreviation raises many problems from the point of view of the theory of word formation. Until now, the question of how legitimate it is to consider abbreviation as one of the methods of word formation is being discussed. There is no complete unity on this issue, however, most researchers recognize the abbreviation as one of the ways of word formation, but significant reservations are made.

Homonymous abbreviations present a particular difficulty for translation. The issue of the recipient's perception of English abbreviations is becoming more and more relevant. Due to the special tendency of the English language to compression, economy of language means, simplification of grammatical structures, we have a well-developed system of abbreviations and broad prospects for its further development. On the one hand, these are endless opportunities for creating ever new abbreviations, their speedy adaptation in the English language system, on the other hand, these are certain difficulties associated with contradictions in this system, with its imperfection.

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